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The Role of Computer Applications in facilitating Artificial Intelligence (AI) Education among Senior Secondary School Students in Benin City

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of computer applications in facilitating artificial intelligence (AI) education among secondary school students in Benin City, Nigeria. Guided by four research questions, the study employs a descriptive survey design with a sample of 750 students selected through multistage sampling. The sample comprised 351 males (46.8%) and 399 females (53.2%), with 84 students (11.2%) from Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), 666 students (88.8%) from Senior Secondary School (SSS 1-3), and equal number of students from both the public and private schools. A structured questionnaire, reviewed by experts for content and face validity, was used to collect data across five sections: demographic information, usage of computer applications, knowledge and awareness of AI, challenges in using computer applications for AI education, and opportunities for AI integration. Pilot testing yielded high-reliability coefficients (0.80–0.88). Data analysis tools used include frequencies, percentages and ranking. The findings reveal limited access to computer

applications and a low level of AI awareness among students. Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teacher training, and a lack of resources were identified as barriers to integrating AI into education. Despite these challenges, the study underscores the necessity of AI education to prepare students for technology-driven careers. Recommendations include increased funding for computer labs, internet connectivity, and electricity in schools, particularly in rural areas. Additionally, teacher training on AI concepts, curriculum updates to include advanced AI topics, and awareness campaigns on AI's importance for future careers are advocated to enhance the integration of AI education in schools.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Education, Computer Applications, Secondary School Students, Educational Technology Integration, AI Awareness

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has transformed the education sector, with artificial intelligence (AI) playing a prominent role in shaping the future of learning. AI has revolutionized industries worldwide, and education systems are increasingly adopting AI to enhance student engagement, deliver personalized learning experiences, and foster critical thinking skills (Zawacki-Richter *et al.*, 2019). In developing countries like Nigeria, where educational challenges persist due to inadequate resources and infrastructure, the integration of AI education holds immense potential to bridge the digital divide and improve learning quality.

Senior secondary school students are at a critical stage in their academic journey, stand to benefit significantly from early exposure to AI concepts. For AI education to succeed, a strong foundation in computer applications is essential, as these tools enable students to interact with AI technologies. However, the use of computer applications in Nigerian secondary schools remains limited due to infrastructural deficits, a lack of trained personnel, and insufficient funding (Oguntoye & Aramide, 2023). These gaps in technological exposure raise concerns about whether Nigerian students are adequately prepared to engage with AI in their curriculum.

Recent initiatives by the Nigerian government and private stakeholders highlight the need for increased technology integration in secondary education. The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) has introduced computer literacy programs and promoted digital learning. Despite these efforts, the widespread adoption of AI education is hindered by limited access to computer applications in schools. Research shows that computer applications when effectively utilized, foster student-centred learning environments, enhance engagement, and improve learning outcomes. Papadakis *et al.* (2021) found that computer applications enable personalized learning by allowing students to work at their own pace while providing teachers with real-time data to assess progress. In AI education, computer applications are foundational tools for introducing programming languages, machine learning algorithms, and robotics.

In Nigeria, computer literacy programs have been introduced in some secondary schools, but their adoption is uneven, with urban schools typically having more access to

these technologies than rural ones (Wordu, 2020). The digital divide between urban and rural students presents a significant barrier to ensuring equitable access to AI education. Without foundational computer skills, students may struggle to comprehend more complex AI concepts such as algorithms and data processing (Eden *et al.*, 2021). Adewale *et al.* (2024) emphasize that the Nigerian curriculum often focuses on basic computing skills, neglecting advanced topics like AI, which are increasingly relevant in the 21st century workforce.

Empirical studies emphasize the importance of early AI exposure in education. For example, Agarry *et al.* (2022) identified AI as a critical component of Nigeria's transition to digital systems, noting students' awareness and willingness to use AI-based learning tools. Adelana and Akinyemi (2021) confirmed students' readiness for AI education through positive attitudes toward adopting AI technologies. Adewale *et al.* (2024) found that AI integration improved student engagement and performance in science subjects, while Ekwu (2025) highlighted AI's role in creating personalized learning experiences at universities. Similarly, Okunade (2024) demonstrated AI's potential to transform secondary education by enhancing engagement, personalized learning, and teacher analytics.

Countries like the United States, China, and India have made significant progress in incorporating AI into their school curricula, promoting digital literacy and preparing students for technology-driven industries (Anderson & Rainie, 2020). In contrast, Nigeria is still in the early stages of exploring the potential of AI education. While other developing countries have invested in digital infrastructure and introduced AI modules in their secondary curricula, Nigeria faces challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to computers, electricity issues and a shortage of teachers trained in AI (Irele, 2020). Wordu (2020) further highlights the disparity in resources between urban and rural schools, which exacerbates inequities in access to digital education.

Teacher preparedness plays a critical role in facilitating the use of computer applications and introducing AI concepts. Adeyemi *et al.* (2022) argue that teachers with digital literacy training are better equipped to create engaging and interactive learning experiences. However, Adeoye *et al.* (2021) emphasize that many Nigerian teachers lack the necessary training to integrate computer applications and AI-related content into their lessons. Although NITDA has implemented initiatives to improve teacher training, these efforts remain limited and inconsistent. Professional development programmes focused on digital education and AI instruction are essential to address these gaps and ensure effective implementation.

The introduction of AI in secondary schools has the potential to enhance students' critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and digital literacy. Holmes *et al.* (2019) and Adelana & Akinyemi (2021) found that early exposure to AI concepts positively impacts cognitive skills, preparing students for future careers in technology-driven industries. According to Okunade (2024), students exposed to AI demonstrated improved performance in subjects like science and mathematics, benefiting from the analytical skills learned through AI education.

Efforts to integrate AI into Nigerian education require a collaborative approach involving government agencies, private stakeholders, and educational institutions. While some progress has been made introducing computer literacy programs, a more comprehensive strategy is needed to address challenges such as resource disparities, teacher training, and curriculum development. Learning from countries like India and China, which have successfully implemented AI education initiatives, Nigeria can take steps to provide equitable access to AI education and prepare its students for the demands of a technology-driven future.

Despite the global shift toward AI and digital literacy, Nigeria faces unique challenges in integrating computer applications into secondary education. Many Nigerian schools lack the basic infrastructure needed for digital education, including electricity, computers, and internet access (Irele, 2020). The limited availability of computer labs in schools hampers students' ability to engage with AI-related software and tools. Teachers often lack the necessary training to incorporate computer applications and AI concepts into their lessons. According to Okoh and Alamu (2024), there is an urgent need for teacher professional development programmes focused on digital education and AI instruction. The Nigerian senior secondary school curriculum is not fully aligned with the demands of 21st-century skills, including AI literacy. While efforts have been made to introduce computer science, these courses are often limited to basic computing skills and do not explore advanced topics such as AI (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2022). This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the role of computer applications in facilitating AI education among senior secondary school students in Benin City, exploring how technology resources, teaching practices and student readiness affect AI learning opportunities.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. To what extent are computer applications currently used to teach AI concepts in Senior Secondary Schools in Benin City?
- ii. What is the level of awareness and readiness among senior secondary school students in Benin City to engage with AI education?
- iii. What challenges do teachers and students face in utilizing computer applications for AI education in these schools?
- iv. What are secondary school views on utilizing computer applications for AI education in schools?

Methodology

The study employs a descriptive survey design, with secondary school students in Benin City as the target population. A total of 750 students were selected using a multistage sampling technique. Among them, 351 students (46.8%) were males, while 399 students (53.2%) were females. In terms of class levels, 84 students (11.2%) were from Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), while 666 students (88.8%) were from Senior Secondary School (SSS 1-3), and equal number of students from both the public and private schools. Additionally, 658

students (87.8%) were from urban schools, while 92 students (12.2%) were from rural schools. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire designed to gather data in five key areas. The first section captured demographic information, including age, gender, class level, and school location. The second section assessed students' frequency and proficiency in using computer applications for learning. The third section evaluated students' knowledge and awareness of artificial intelligence (AI) concepts and tools. The fourth section explored challenges in using computer applications for AI education, such as lack of resources or technical skills. The fifth section examined opportunities for AI education, focusing on AI's potential benefits and integration into the educational system. To ensure validity, the instrument was reviewed by experts in Educational Technology and Measurement. A pilot test was conducted with 50 students outside the main sample, resulting in Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients of 0.80, 0.84, 0.83, and 0.88 for the respective sections. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, and ranking.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent are computer applications currently used to teach AI concepts in Senior Secondary Schools in Benin City?

Table 1: Computer Applications Currently Used to Teach AI Concepts in Senior Secondary Schools in Benin City

Statement			Yes (%)	No (%)
Do you have access to computers in your school?			194 (25.9)	556 (74.1)
Do you have access to the internet in your school?			270 (36.1)	480 (63.9)
How often do you use computer applications in your school for learning	Daily	Weekly	Occasionally	Never
	76 (10.1)	160(21.3)	511 (68.1)	01(0.5)
Which of the following computer applications are you familiar with	Microsoft Words	Coding Platform	Graphic Design	Web Browsers
	307(40.9)	48(6.4)	220(29.3)	176(23.4)
How confident are you in using computer applications	Very Confident	Confident	Neutral	Not Confident at all
	28(3.8)	280(37.3)	280(37.3)	162(21.6)
Do you have access to personal computers outside the school			Yes	No
			325(43.4)	425(56.6)
How much time do you spend using computers for learning per week?	Less than 1 hour	1 – 3 hours	4-6 hours	More than 6 hours
	415(55.4)	246(32.8)	55(7.3)	34(4.5)

The data in Table 1 indicates that only 25.9% of students had access to computers, and 36.1% had access to the Internet in their schools. A majority (68.1%) reported occasional use of computer applications for learning. Furthermore, just 40.9% were familiar with Microsoft Office, the primary computer application software they used, while only 37.3%

felt confident using computer applications. Additionally, only 43.4% of students had access to personal computers outside of school. Regarding time spent using computers for learning outside school hours, the majority (55.4%) spent less than one hour per week.

Research Question Two

What is the level of awareness and readiness among senior secondary school students in Benin City to engage with AI education?

Table 2: The Level of Awareness and Readiness Among Senior Secondary School Students in Benin City to Engage with AI Education

Statement	Yes (%)		No (%)		
Have you heard about artificial intelligence (AI)?	161 (21.5)		589 (78.5)		
If yes, where did you learn about AI?	School	Internet/social media	TV/Radio	Friends/Family	
	38(23.6)	74(45.8)	19(11.8)	30(18.8)	
Which of the following AI-related concepts are you familiar with?	Daily	Weekly	Occasionally	Never	
	76 (10.1)	160(21.3)	511 (68.1)	01(0.5)	
Which of the following computer applications are you familiar with	Machine Learning	Robotics	Data analysis	Natural language Processing	AI ethics
	119(15.9)	196(26.1)	199(26.5)	107(14.3)	129 (17.2)
Have you been taught any AI-related concepts in your school?	Yes		No		
	398 (53.1)		352 (46.9)		
If yes, which applications were used to teach AI concepts in your school	Coding	Robotics	Simulations	Others	
	243(61.1)	80(20.0)	70(17.6)	5(1.2)	
How would you rate your understanding of AI concepts taught in school	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	None
	118(15.7)	72(9.6)	185(24.7)	303(40.4)	72(9.6)

The data in Table 2 reveals that the majority of students (78.5%) were unaware of artificial intelligence. Among the 21.5% who were aware, 45.8% had learned about it through the internet and social media. Only 26.5% of students were familiar with data analysis as an AI-related concept. Regarding exposure to AI-related topics in school, 53.1% indicated they had been taught, with coding being the most commonly taught concept (61.1%). However, when asked to rate their understanding of AI-related concepts taught in school, a significant portion (40.4%) rated their understanding as poor.

Research Question Three

What challenges do teachers and students face in utilizing computer applications for AI education in these schools?

Table 3: Challenges Teachers and Students Face in Utilizing Computer Applications For AI Education in Schools

Challenges	Frequencies	Ranks
Lack of access to computers	77	6
Poor internet connectivity	79	4
Lack of trained teachers	27	10
Lack of relevant software	64	7
Insufficient time for practice	148	1
Lack of AI-related resources	78	5
Lack of teacher knowledge	57	8
Limited computer access	86	2
AI not included in the curriculum	82	3
No exposure to AI concepts	50	9

The data in Table 3 reveals that the primary challenge in utilizing computer applications for artificial intelligence education is insufficient time for practice. This is followed by limited access to computers, the absence of artificial intelligence in the curriculum, a lack of AI-related resources such as software and tools, inadequate computer availability, and poor internet connectivity. Conversely, minimal exposure to AI concepts and the shortage of trained teachers were identified as the least significant challenges.

Research Question Four

What are secondary school views on utilizing computer applications for AI education in schools?

Table 4: Opportunities for Artificial Intelligence Education

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Do you think learning AI is important for your future?	12(1.6)	12(1.6)	429 (57.2)	297 (39.6)
Would you be interested in learning more about AI through computer applications?			Yes 157(21.0)	No 293(79.0)
What types of computer applications do you think can help you learn AI more effectively?	Coding Platforms 199(26.6)	Simulation tools 197(26.2)	AI-based games 155(20.6)	Robotics kits 199(26.6)
How motivated are you to learn AI if more computer applications were available in your school?	Very Motivated 20(2.7)	Motivated 28(3.7)	Not Motivated 311(41.5)	Not Motivated at all 391(52.1)

The data in Table 4 reveals that only a small percentage (3.2%) of students view artificial intelligence as important for their future careers. The majority (79.0%) expressed no interest in learning more about AI through computer applications. Regarding the types of computer applications they believe could effectively aid in learning AI, 26.6% and 26.2% selected coding platforms and simulation tools, respectively. When asked about their motivation to learn AI with the increased availability of computer applications in schools, more than half (52.1%) stated that they would not be motivated at all.

Discussion

The study reveals several critical insights regarding the role of computer applications in facilitating artificial intelligence (AI) education among senior secondary school students in Benin City, Nigeria. One of the most prominent findings is the limited access to computers and the Internet in schools. According to the results, only 25.9% of students had access to computers and 36.1% had access to the internet in their schools. This limitation is compounded by the fact that a significant portion of students (68.1%) report using computer applications only occasionally for learning purposes. Inadequate resources, including a lack of sufficient time for practice, were also identified as key barriers, with 40.9% of students reporting familiarity with Microsoft Office as the most common software, indicating a reliance on basic computing tools.

The study also reveals a concerning gap in students' awareness and understanding of AI. The majority (78.5%) of students were unaware of artificial intelligence, and of the 21.5% who were aware, many only encountered AI concepts via the internet and social media. Furthermore, only 26.5% of students were familiar with data analysis as an AI-related concept. These findings underscore the inadequacy of current curricular offerings, as students are only exposed to limited aspects of AI, with coding being the most commonly taught concept (61.1%). The fact that a substantial portion (40.4%) rated their understanding of AI-related topics as poor indicates the need for a more comprehensive and structured AI curriculum to enhance students' conceptual knowledge and technical skills. Akinyemi *et al.* (2022) emphasize that AI education must go beyond rudimentary computing skills, incorporating advanced topics to better prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century workforce. The results suggest that Nigeria's current secondary school curriculum does not adequately meet these needs.

Moreover, the study's findings reveal a lack of motivation and interest in AI education among students. While a few students recognized the potential of coding platforms and simulation tools to aid in AI learning, the majority (79.0%) expressed no desire to learn more about AI. Only a small percentage (3.2%) perceived AI as relevant to their future careers. This lack of interest is a significant challenge, as student engagement is critical to the success of any educational initiative (Papadakis *et al.*, 2021). Raising awareness about the potential benefits of AI education and its relevance to future career prospects is essential. Strategies to increase motivation could include integrating hands-on activities, creating opportunities for practical experiences, and incorporating AI into the curriculum as a core subject (Adelana & Akinyemi, 2021).

In terms of challenges, the study revealed that the absence of AI-specific resources, such as AI-related software and tools, compounded the difficulties faced by both teachers and students. Insufficient time for practice, along with the absence of AI in the curriculum, were the primary obstacles reported. The lack of trained teachers in AI and the minimal exposure to AI-related topics in school further contributed to the challenges. These findings align with Adeoye *et al.* (2021), who argue that teacher preparedness is crucial for the effective integration of AI into the classroom. Adequate teacher training programs focusing on digital literacy and AI concepts are necessary to overcome these challenges and foster a deeper understanding of AI in secondary school education.

The study's findings also point to the need for a more collaborative approach to AI education in Nigeria. While government initiatives like those by NITDA (Olumide & Abimbola, 2022) have made strides in promoting computer literacy, a more comprehensive strategy is required to ensure equitable access to digital education across both urban and rural areas. The digital divide between urban and rural schools, as highlighted by Wordu (2020), is a significant barrier to achieving this goal. To address these disparities, more investments in digital infrastructure, teacher training, and AI-specific curriculum development are necessary.

Conclusion

This study assessed the role of computer applications in facilitating Artificial Intelligence (AI) education among senior secondary school students in Benin City, Nigeria. The findings revealed significant gaps in access to and use of computer applications in schools, particularly for AI education. While some students had limited exposure to AI-related concepts, their knowledge and awareness were generally low. The study also highlighted challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited teacher training, and insufficient access to resources, which hinder the effective integration of AI into the curriculum. Despite these challenges, there is an evident need for AI education as a means to prepare students for future technology-driven careers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following were recommended

- i. The government and stakeholders should prioritize funding for the installation of computer labs, provision of internet connectivity, and electricity in schools, especially in rural areas.
- ii. Teachers should undergo regular training on the integration of computer applications and AI concepts into the curriculum.
- iii. The national curriculum should be reviewed and updated to include more advanced AI concepts such as machine learning, robotics, and data analysis.
- iv. Schools should create awareness campaigns to help students understand the importance of AI education and its relevance to their future careers.

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